

Editorial

Anti-fibrotic role of IL-15 in chronic pancreatitis

Murli Manohar, PhD*

Department of Medicine, Section of Pulmonary Diseases, Tulane University School of Medicine, New Orleans, LA 70112.

(Received Nov 28, 2018; Accepted December 18, 2018)

Chronic pancreatitis (CP) is progressive pancreatic inflammatory disorder of pancreas that is assumed to drive from repeated episodes of acute pancreatitis (AP). The main causes of CP are alcohol, smoking, duct obstruction, and genetic factors [1]. A small percentage of CP patients may also develop as pancreatic malignancy [2]. During the pathogenesis of CP several types of immune cells such as eosinophils, monocytes, macrophages, and mast cells that secretes pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines are known to play an important role in CP pathogenesis [3-8]. CP is mainly characterized by scarring, loss of exocrine and endocrine pancreatic insufficiency and extensive pancreatic fibrosis i.e. driven by pancreatic stellate cells (PSCs) [3, 9]. However, the lack of active therapy for management of CP due to high level of pancreatic fibrosis i.e. (an irreversible process) needs further

attention to develop effective treatment. Therefore, restriction in the progression of fibrosis could be novel strategy for the treatment of CP pathogenesis. IL-15 is an important cytokine with 15kDa molecular weight and involved in innate and acquired immunity. IL-15 has a critical role in the growth and survival of natural killer (NK) and NKT cells [10-14]. IL-15 mediates its mode of action via its receptor i.e. IL-15R α but also binds to the common cytokine γ -chain (CD132) IL-2/IL-15 receptor that shares receptor β (IL-15R β) (CD122) [15, 16]. NK and NKT cells have ability to destroy certain tumor cells by secreting interferon gamma (IFN γ) and reports indicates NK and NKT cells derived interferon γ (IFN- γ) [17-19] is involved in the improvement of acute pancreatitis [20]. Serum IL-15 level act as a predictor of complication and mortality in severe acute pancreatitis

*Current Address for M Manohar: School of Medicine, GI and Hepatology Division, Stanford University, CA, 94304

[21] and IL-15 serve as a protective factor against organ injury in the severe acute pancreatitis [22, 23]. Notably, a report demonstrates that IL-15 activated natural NK cells have ability to kill human PSCs and pancreatic cancer cell lines [24]. Yoshida et al, have reported that IL 15 producing pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells reveal a tumor-shrinking effect via NK cells [25]. Human umbilical cord blood-derived mesenchymal stem cells secretes IL-15 is capable of eradicating pancreatic tumors in mice [26]. Recently, we showed that pharmacological treatment of recombinant (r) IL-15 improves remodeling and fibrosis in cerulein-induced chronic pancreatitis in mice [5]. By using IL-15 deficient mice we showed role of IL-15 in promoting tissue fibrosis and IL-15 deficient mice showed induced pancreatic remodeling including collagen and profibrotic cytokines i.e. TGF- β . Further, we found atrophy of pancreatic acinar cells, induced inflammatory response, increased collagen deposition, and up-regulated protein level of TGF- β 1, α -SMA, and collagen-1 in cerulein-induced chronic pancreatitis in mice. Interestingly, 5ug intravenous (i.v.) dose of rIL-15 for 4 weeks (once in a week) protects mice from the cerulein-induced chronic pancreatitis pathogenesis including acinar cells atrophy, and perivascular accumulation of tissue collagen

followed by down-regulation of pro-fibrotic genes such as TGF- β 1, α -SMA, Collagen-1, Collagen-3, and Fibronectin in cerulein-induced chronic pancreatitis in mice. Mechanistically, we demonstrated the novel role of IL-15 responsive NKT cells and derived cytokines INF- γ in the pathogenesis of cerulein induced chronic pancreatitis in mice. We showed were decreased in cerulein-induced chronic pancreatitis; whereas, rIL-15 treatment in cerulein-treated mice showed increased numbers of NKT cells and may be involved in improving the pancreatitis pathogenesis in mice [25]. We also identified that STAT5 signaling may regulate IL-15 mediated protection in cerulein-induced pancreatitis via activating NKT cells-induced innate responses. In conclusion, our findings provide the evidence that rIL-15 may be a possible and potential therapeutic target strategy for the treatment of pancreatic fibrosis during chronic pancreatitis. The current study proposes rIL-15 or its agonist (i.e. ALT-803 with longer half-life over IL-15) multi-central clinical trial may be able to restrict fibrosis in chronic pancreatitis patients.

Conflicts of interest

We declare that we have no professional or personal affiliations with any organization or entity with a

financial or non-financial interest related to the topics presented in this manuscript that could influence the positions stated.

References

1. Pham, A. and C. Forsmark, Chronic pancreatitis: review and update of etiology, risk factors, and management. *F1000Res*, 2018. **7**.
2. Patel, V. and F. Willingham, The Management of Chronic Pancreatitis. *Med Clin North Am*, 2019. **103**(1): p. 153-162.
3. Manohar, M., et al., Pathogenic mechanisms of pancreatitis. *World J Gastrointest Pharmacol Ther*, 2017. **8**(1): p. 10-25.
4. Manohar, M., et al., Role of eosinophils in the initiation and progression of pancreatitis pathogenesis. *Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol*, 2017: p. ajpgi 00210 2017.
5. Manohar, M., et al., IL-15 regulates fibrosis and inflammation in a mouse model of chronic pancreatitis. *Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol*, 2018, Sep 13. doi: 10.1152/ajpgi.00139.2018.
6. Manohar, M., Eosinophilic pancreatitis need an attention. *J Pulmonol Clin Res.* , 2017. **1**(1): p. 1-2.
7. Manohar M, V.A., Venkateshaiah SU, Mishra A, Immunological Responses Involved In Promoting Acute and Chronic Pancreatitis. . *J Clin Immunol Res*, 2017. **1**: p. 1-8.
8. Manohar, M., et al., Significance of Eosinophils in Promoting Pancreatic malignancy. *J Gastroenterol Pancreatol Liver Disord*, 2017. **5**(1).
9. Manohar M, V.A., Venkateshaiah SU, Sanders NL, Mishra A *Chronic Pancreatitis Associated Acute Respiratory Failure*. *MOJ. Immunology*, 2017. **5**(2): p. 1-7
10. Diab, A., et al., *IL-15: targeting CD8+ T cells for immunotherapy*. *Cytotherapy*, 2005. **7**(1): p. 23-35.
11. Ohteki, T., *Critical role for IL-15 in innate immunity*. *Curr Mol Med* 2002. **2**(4): p. 371-80.
12. Nicholson, S.E., N. Keating, and G.T. Belz, *Natural killer cells and anti-tumor immunity*. *Mol Immunol*, 2017.
13. Mishra, A., L. Sullivan, and M.A. Caligiuri, *Molecular pathways: interleukin-15 signaling in health and in cancer*. *Clin Cancer Res*, 2014. **20**(8): p. 2044-50.
14. Huntington, N.D., *The unconventional expression of IL-15 and its role in NK cell homeostasis*. *Immunol Cell Biol*, 2014. **92**(3): p. 210-3.
15. Tamzalit, F., et al., *IL-15.IL-15Ralpha complex shedding following trans-presentation is essential for the survival of IL-15 responding NK and T cells*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 2014. **111**(23): p. 8565-70.
16. Giri, J.G., et al., *IL-15, a novel T cell growth factor that shares activities and receptor components with IL-2*. *J Leukoc Biol*, 1995. **57**(5): p. 763-6.

17. Wang, R., et al., *Natural killer cell-produced IFN-gamma and TNF-alpha induce target cell cytolysis through up-regulation of ICAM-1*. J Leukoc Biol, 2012. **91**(2): p. 299-309.
18. Olson, C.M., Jr., et al., *Local production of IFN-gamma by invariant NKT cells modulates acute Lyme carditis*. J Immunol 2009. **182**(6): p. 3728-34.
19. Arase, H., N. Arase, and T. Saito, *Interferon gamma production by natural killer (NK) cells and NK1.1+ T cells upon NKR-P1 cross-linking*. J Exp. Med, 1996. **183**(5): p. 2391-6.
20. Hayashi, T., et al., *IFN-gamma protects cerulein-induced acute pancreatitis by repressing NF kappa B activation*. J Immunol, 2007. **178**(11): p. 7385-94.
21. Kamei, K., et al., *Significant expression of interleukin 15 in rat experimental severe acute pancreatitis*. Eur Surg Res, 2010. **44**(3-4): p. 159-69.
22. Ueda, T., *Serum interleukin-15 level in patients with severe acute pancreatitis*. Surgery, 2008. **143**(5): p. 695-6.
23. Ueda, T., et al., *Serum interleukin-15 level is a useful predictor of the complications and mortality in severe acute pancreatitis*. Surgery, 2007. **142**(3): p. 319-26.
24. Van Audenaerde, J.R.M., et al., *Interleukin-15 stimulates natural killer cell-mediated killing of both human pancreatic cancer and stellate cells*. Oncotarget, 2017. **8**(34): p. 56968-56979.
25. Yoshida, Y., et al., *Impaired tumorigenicity of human pancreatic cancer cells retrovirally transduced with interleukin-12 or interleukin-15 gene*. Cancer Gene Ther, 2000. **7**(2): p. 324-31.
26. Jing, W., et al., *Human umbilical cord blood-derived mesenchymal stem cells producing IL-15 eradicate established pancreatic tumor in syngeneic mice*. Mol Cancer Ther, 2014. **13**(8): p. 2127-37.

